

STUDIES ON A POSSIBILITY OF USING COMPOSITE MATERIALS
FOR CONSTRUCTING AUTOMOBILE IN THE THIRD GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports results of studies centering on a possibility of using composite materials for constructing automobile bodies in the future.

In pursuing the possibility, efforts were made to reduce the weight and improve performance of small passenger cars by making the body primarily with carbonfiber reinforced plastics (CFRP), especially by means of integrating the chassis and suspensions.

An attempt was made to apply composite materials having controlled fiber orientation and consisting of thermoplastic resin matrix and continuous fiber reinforcement, to making a vehicle body.

Discussion focused on an idea of car body having elliptical springs that integrate with suspensions which continuously branch out from the chassis.

The next step was to design a structure based on such a concept.

A prototype was then created of vehicle body having elliptical spring made of fiber orientation-controlled CFRTF in which poly-ether-ether-ketone (PEEK) and polycarbonate (PC) resin were used as matrix.

As the result of a characteristic analysis of the prototype, the body weight of the car was estimated to be approximately 143kg. It was estimated further that such a light weight design will reduce fuel consumption of the car to about half, provided that the engine output remains unchanged.

INTRODUCTION

This paper concerns a study conducted in pursuit of a possibility of using composite materials for building what may be called third-generation automobile bodies in the 21st century.

The major target of the study is to build an auto body of a small passenger vehicle using new materials and reduce its energy requirement to one half of fuel consumption of vehicles of the same size powered by existing engines.

Such a target can be accomplished if dynamic characteristics of composite materials themselves are fully utilized, provided that applicable elementary technologies will be more advanced in further than they are today.

PREDICTED CONDITIONS OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR CONSTRUCTING AUTOMOBILE BODIES

Fig.1 shows conditions of composite materials appropriate for making automobile bodies. These conditions are predicted on the basis of prevailing composite material technologies.

In using composite materials for making automobiles, much is expected of high productivity that will be implemented by combining advanced fibers of high performance and thermoplastic resins of outstanding toughness. Continuous long fiber reinforcement and orientation-controlled fibers will be arranged automatically to make automobile bodies. Additional efforts should be made regarding disposal and re-use of material waste.

Fig.1 Predicted conditions of composite materials for making automobile body structures

WEIGHT-REDUCTING TECHNOLOGIES AND USE OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

This study assumes that carbon fiber technology will mark further progress in future. Carbon fiber exel, and will in future exel even more, in strength, rigidity and elasticity, and they may be used to make springs benefiting from these outstanding physical features.

Their excellent damping force will provide a base for a new kind of automobile design concept. By continuously altering the fiber orientation and density of composite structural materials of an automobile body, taking both the body shape and material composition into consideration, it is predicted that it is possible to integrate the chassis and the suspension into a unit structure that will satisfy all conditions required by the behavior of wheels.

Orientation of high-performance fibers will ensure a three-dimensional degree of freedom. Designers will be able to design automobile bodies with an entirely different kind of freedom that is not available from monolithic materials such as metals.

This suggests an important and overall change in functions of components, each having a unique function, vehicles that are made of composite materials as proposed in this paper will have a monocoque (unitized) body which is an organic integration of composite materials. When implemented, it will be a vehicle that is steps closer to a living creature.

Composite materials may be used in combination with steel constructions as in some supposedly "light weight" vehicles that exit today. But a drastic weight reduction cannot be expected from such use of composite materials. This paper proposes an integration of conventionally separate component; the body frame, the chassis and the suspensions.

Fig.2 shows functional relations among composite materials and systems that will make a unitized auto body.

Fig.2 Process of body and chassis integration

CONCEPTUAL DESIGNS OF AUTOMOBILE STRUCTURES MADE OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Integration of elliptical springs

Elliptical FRP springs have been proposed for automobiles by such pioneers as P.K.Mallick ¹⁾ and J.M.ChARRIER ²⁾. Those springs indicate interesting characteristics that are not found in conventional leaf springs.

CFRP spring models were prepared for the purpose of this paper, as shown in photo 1.

Photo. 1 CFRTP ELLIPTICAL SPRING MODELS

Three different types of matrixes were used, namely polyether-ether ketone (PEEK), polycarbonate (PC) and polyamide (Nylon-6) matrixes. Three models were prepared for each matrix, having three different fiber orientations (uni-directional, $\pm 45^\circ$ and $0^\circ/90^\circ$). Result of dynamic analysis of those models are reported separately by T.Akasaka and others³⁾.

A dynamic analysis of those models suggests that spring constants can be adjusted via elliptical springs rather than on tires alone. This provides a major advantage in using composite materials to make "tailor made" spring structures.

Fig.3 shows a conceptual drawing of rear suspension system as an example of unitized auto body that integrates elliptical springs as proposed in this paper. In this particular drawing, the suspension branches out from a rigid body-chassis structure and elliptical springs are integrated with the suspension.

Fig.4 shows a concept of entire body structure and Fig.5 and Fig.6 shows some examples of design integrating composite material components that are divided into body parts. Assuming an automobile body structure entirely consisting of CFRP plus surface-refined transparent plastics window glass that replace where glass normally used, such a body will weigh approximately 143kg only

Fig.3 A CONCEPTUAL DRAWING OF REAR SUSPENSION

Fig.4 CONCEPTUAL DESIGN OF AN ENTIRE BODY STRUCTURE

Fig.5 DIVIDED COMPONENTS OF BODY PARTS

Fig.6 A EXAMPLE OF DESIGN FOR INTEGRATING COMPONENTS

Photo.2 shows a mock-up model.

Photo.2 A MOCK-UP MODEL

CONCLUSION

The most important performance of a structure made of composite material is weight reduction which promises a higher fuel efficiency and other favorable results that belong to truly light weight vehicles. It has adverse effects also that need to be solved, such as the effect of wind and road holding when the vehicle is running.

It is assumed that efforts will be made in future to install, under the body floor, a fuel tank or even a container of metallic alloys for hydrogen storage that will be developed as a source of clean energy replacing conventional petroleum fuels.

There exist many more problems that need to be tackled. They include a need to improve basic performance of the body to a practically reliable level. Appropriate production engineering and maintenance methods must be developed also.

This paper proposes just one of many possibilities for using composite materials to make automobile bodies of the future, including possibilities for solving those problems.

This paper constitutes a part of the total report of a study that was conducted from 1984 to 1986 by JAPAN AUTOMOBILE RESEARCH INSTITUTE at a request of RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE OF METALS AND COMPOSITES FOR FUTURE INDUSTRIES.

REFERENCES

1. P.K.Mallick: "Design and Development of Composite Elliptic Springs for Automotive Suspensions"; Proc. 40th SPT, Sess.14-C, 1986.
2. J.M.Charrier, R.Connolly, S.G.Maki:"End-Loading of Filament Wound Circular and Elliptic FRP Rings Spring Element Applications"; Proc. 41st SPI, Sess. 24-B, 1987.
3. T.Akasaka, M.Masutani, T.Nakakura, H.Sakai: " Spring Constants of Elliptic Rings Made of Carbon-Fiber-Reinforced Thermoplastics"; Proc. 33rd Int. SAMPE Symp., pp. 670-680, 1988